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Contactless Sanitizer and Water Dispenser: A Need of Hour

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Abstract

In such a surge of ongoing pandemic in geographical areas across the state of Uttar Pradesh and India, the onus of protecting citizens lies entirely on the corona warriors. This paper has aligned itself to protection that we can offer to these corona warriors by means of offering them- contactless hand sanitizer cum drinking water dispenser - at their duty posts like market areas, police stations, streets, hospitals, nursing homes, ambulances etc.

Keywords- *Contactless Hand Sanitizer and Drinking water dispenser, Sensor based dispenser, Corona warriors, Covid infection, corona protocol, LSR*

I. INTRODUCTION

Problem domain: During the pandemic, it is very difficult to source sanitizer [1] to clean our hands especially when the facility is not around, leading to distraction of the personnel on duty.

II. MOTIVATION

Police stations in the state of Uttar Pradesh saw a lot many officials passing away due to corona virus infection. An estimate of 162 officers died in Uttar Pradesh(UP) police force.. 4117UP Police personnels suffered from the infection with multiples across India[Source State and Central Government records].The Indian Medical Association had announced that at least 34 doctors have died in the second wave in UP with 594 doctor deaths across India[Source Indian Medical Association(IMA)]

After going through validated experiences and narrowing down to this scenario that this is a problematic issue amidst the surging pandemic, and that there is a need to work and develop the contactless hand sanitizer cum drinking water dispenser.

III. PAPER OBJECTIVE

This throws light on the necessity of Contactless Hand Sanitizer [2,3] and Drinking Water Dispenser and the design of its MVP Minimum Viable Prototype.

A. Role of stakeholders in implementation and sustainability

1) Initial implementation – As a pilot project, our team has gone to the users to get the initial problem issue related to hand wash, the responses received were validate to start with this device.

2) Future implementation – The team will visit the facilities of this device installation to get real time feedback on its efficacy through random sampling method

IV. INTRODUCTION

1) As a part of sustainable development, with time these devices can be scaled up to more officials with better features as recommended by the end users. These feedbacks shall be frequently collated and analysed by our PSIT IEEE Student Branch team in Kanpur city.

B. Dissemination of achievements and lessons learned

We developed a feedback form on paper for the personnel’s in police services and health services to analyses their experience on device usage. The ratings were – Excellent, Good, and Satisfactory. We got the following ratings out of 50 respondents. We observed that contactless sanitizer and water dispenser is now need of hour. If all the institutions will be equipped with the same device, we can make our working environment free from viruses.

Ratings	Excellent	Good	Satisfactory
Sanitiser dispenser	22	18	10
Water dispenser	28	12	10

Figure 1: An analysis of hand sanitizer and water dispenser

V. RESEARCH TECHNOLOGY

A. Construction and Working Methodology

Connection of submersible pump with L293 motor driver: Connect Vcc and ground motor for water with L293D output A. Connect Vcc and ground for motor for sanitizer with L293D output B

1) For inverting the signal of IR sensor:

Transistor is used as inverting signal-Signal Pin of IR sensor is connected to base of transistor with 10K ohm resistor.GND pin of IR sensor and emitter is connected to ground.VCC pin of IR sensor is connected with 1K ohm resistor, which is connected to collector of transistor. (VCC with 5V).The output will be the inverse of input signal.

Conversion of 9V to 5V using 7805 Voltage regulator IC-Connect 9v DC adapter Vcc with input of 7805 voltage regulator with 100uf capacitor.Connect negative pin of adapter with gnd of 7805.At the output side, 100uf capacitor positive side is connected with output of 7805 and negative pin with groundConversion of 9V to 5V using 7805 Voltage regulator IC

2) Connection of IR sensor with L293D motor driver

First we will connect VCC of IR sensor and motor driver to bread board then connect +5v of IR sensor to the (+) terminal of VCC and (-) of IR sensor to the ground of the motor driver.Now, we have connected signal pin of IR sensor to the (input 1) of the motor driver and second IR sensor with input 4 of motor driver. Connect positive terminal of the battery with Vcc of both IR sensor and driver.Connect Negative terminal of the battery with ground of both IR sensor.Adjust the range of IR sensor by rotating its potentiometer.

Fig. 1. Circuit Block Diagram

To make circuit waterproof we applied glue gun to prevent it from damaging the circuit. To protect the circuit from external damage we fit the circuit inside steel box.

VI. WORKING MECHANISM OF THE DEVICE

It consists of a metal tank. It encompasses another metal tank inside it for a strong casing. In the outer strong tank, this device keeps hand sanitizer and between the inner and the outer tank, this device keeps drinkable water. Upon supply of 220 V AC electricity, it is activated ready to sense and dispense the sanitizer or the drinking water accordingly, as the case may be for the personnel. When the hands approach the sensors, pumps sense the hands, are activated and dispensed. It applies in the case of drinking water.

A. Tools and components used in the making:

1. Drill machine/ rubber sheet/ metal tank – stainless steel of 10-liter capacity/ steel box for circuitry.
2. Tank of 0.5-liter capacity for sanitizer storage.
3. Submersible motor pump
4. Electronic components – L293D Motor driver/ submersible pump with pipe.
5. Mini breadboard/ 9 V 1 A Adapter / IR sensors – 2 / BC547 NPN Transistor - 2
6. 1kohm Resistors – 2 / 7805 Voltage regulator IC / Jumper wires / Capacitors 100 μ F– 2

Fig. 2. Prototype of Contactless Sanitizer and Water Dispenser

Relevance of the device to the corona warriors and the local environment. During the development of this Minimum Viable Prototype (MVP), we took care to use high quality steel and sensors which have a longevity of 3-4 years

With reference to the initial feedback collection for further modifications in our device, we got down to improve upon results achieved from data analysis. We increased our water tank capacity from 5 litres to 10 litres and sanitiser tank capacity from 1 litre to 3 litres. Our proposed methods of data analysis are in sync with data findings. These small interventions led to strengthening the device features and improving upon the limitations of lesser fluids at disposal.

Upon the feel of requirement of sanitizing [4,5] our hands, we tend to search for a sanitising bottle or similar device but with the development and introduction of this device, corona warriors have a dedicated “for the purpose” device installed at their duty posts for cops (traffic and law enforcing cops) and health workers (doctors, nurses, ward boys and ambulance crew). Our development team and volunteers can give a demonstration on device’s importance, its functionality, its alarm system, its filling of sanitizer and drinking water and its repair training to the focus segment of corona warriors and select few would also be trained on its repair.

VII. CONTINGENCY PLAN FOR OUR TEAM

We have three developers working together with good basics into Physics. In case of any one member falling sick, our other members shall continue to work towards project completion. Besides our Team B is always there which can replace Team A in case of any contingency. Interdisciplinary group of social activists, researchers and engineers provided input during the development stages.

VIII. PERCEIVED WEAKNESS AND STRENGTH

With so many devices similar to what we made can be a matter of thought but ours with a water dispenser made it appreciable by the local people and is very relevant and contextual. We resorted to proper data analysis through random sampling and were able to bring in required changes into the device.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In a bid to keep the citizens protected at their ends our corona warriors need to be protected too from the print of virus on their hands while performing their duties in and off the field, touch less hand sanitizer is of great value to these people. These corona warriors [6] are leaving

behind their family members back at their homes to keep the society safe at large by enforcing corona protocol in public places but what if they themselves get infected due to absence of hand hygiene which experts have advocated so much about while following covid appropriate behavior and corona protocol of maintaining safe distance, wearing face mask and keeping hand hygiene [7].

Fig. 3. Prototype testing at Police Station and Medical Center via Police Officers & Doctors

X. CONCLUSION

With a population of 4 million at Kanpur, is the largest industrial hub of Uttar Pradesh To help them conduct their work without hindrance of hygiene for hand, in mind, this device's introduction speaks a lot for deployment at the public service points. This is a device suitable to Low Resource Settings (LRS) and middle and lower income countries.

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